

Effects of Sodium Borohydride Addition on Hypochlorite Bleaching of *Pinus brutia* Pulp

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Abstract – In this study, the effects of adding sodium borohydride (NaBH₄) to the hypochlorite bleaching process of *Pinus brutia* pulp on the bleaching yield and some optical and mechanical properties of the pulp were investigated. The pulps obtained by the sulfate process were bleached with 10% hypochlorite and the NaBH₄ chemical was added at 0.5%, 1.0% and 1.5% to the bleaching processes under the same conditions. After the bleaching processes, the bleaching yield of the pulps was calculated and test papers with 80 grammages (g/m²) were produced. The whiteness and brightness values of the conditioned papers and their tensile and burst strength were determined in compliance with the relevant standards. The pulp whiteness and brightness values were found to increase in parallel with increases in the added NaBH₄ charge. When 1.5% NaBH₄ was added to the hypochlorite bleaching process, it was found that the whiteness increased by 6.3% and the brightness value increased by 14.7%. No significant change was observed in the tensile and burst strengths. In line with these results, it will be possible to obtain higher optical properties with NaBH₄ to be added to the bleaching liquor in conventional hypochlorite bleaching processes, as well as to obtain the desired values by reducing the amount of hypochlorite used.

Keywords – Pulp, Hypochlorite, Sodium Borohydride, Bleaching, *Pinus brutia*

I. INTRODUCTION

With the discovery of writing, people used papyrus and parchment to write. After that, attempts were made to find an alternative to papyrus and parchment in order to be able to write it easily and cheaply. Modern paper was invented around in China. Ts'ai Lun, who was in charge of the Han Dynasty of China in 105, started making paper by pioneering the papermaking industry. Ts'ai Lun cut mulberry bark and hemp rag into thin pieces with the help of water, and then dried them under the sun while removing the water to make his own paper. This work he has done has attracted a lot of attention and has been used throughout China (Gaspar et al., 2010; Hamilton et al., n.d., p. 7; Thompson, 1978).

Wood consists mainly of fibers, with only a few non-fibrous parts such as pith and parenchyma cells. However, due to the Forest Protection Act,

the procurement of wood raw materials has become difficult (Çiçekler et al., 2022). Paper manufacturers are looking for alternative ways to reduce paper and paper packaging expenses. One of the most important steps to reduce costs is to increase pulp yield. The yield is an important parameter in terms of economics in the manufacture of pulp from raw materials such as wood and annual plants and the bleaching of the pulp produced (Gominho et al., 2001; Hailu & Veeman, 2000; Van Heiningen, 2006).

Bleaching is a chemical technique used to improve the appearance of cellulosic materials. With the bleaching process, it is possible to improve the range of use and consumption of the paper. The bleaching process uses appropriate chemical substances and processes to alter and/or eliminate lignin and lignin breakdown products, extractive substances, metal ions, non-cellulose

carbohydrate components and all coloring ingredients in paper (Singh et al., 2015; Sjöström et al., 2000; Tutuş et al., 2017). Sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) is stable above pH 10. It is an inexpensive oxidizer with a greater redox potential than hydrogen peroxide that bleaches rapidly at ambient temperature (Bhardwaj et al., 2019; Ninawe & Kuhad, 2006; Sharma et al., 2020; Trautmann et al., 2021; Tutuş et al., 2017). It also removes natural colorants, lignin and other impurities from the fibers. As it is not a selective bleaching agent, it acts not only on lignin but also on cellulose (Trautmann et al., 2021).

Borohydride is one of the most common boron compounds used in pulp production. Borohydride is generally used to increase the yield of the pulp obtained by adding it to the cooking liquor in certain proportions, and it is also used for bleaching of pulp because it has a bleaching property (Çiçekler et al., 2021; Gulsoy & Eroglu, 2011; Gümüşkaya et al., 2011; İstek & Özkan, 2008; Li et al., 2015; Zhibin et al., 2005). NaBH₄ is increasingly being employed as a reducing agent in multi-stage bleaching processes. It is more effective than sodium or zinc hydrosulfite at converting carbonyl groups to alcohol groups and improving reflectivity across a larger range (Dang et al., 2007).

In this study, the effects of NaBH₄ addition in hypochlorite bleaching of *Pinus brutia* pulp on bleaching yield and optical and mechanical properties of papers were investigated.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

In this study, pulp obtained from *Pinus brutia* woods by kraft method was used. The whiteness, brightness, breaking length and burst index of the pulp used are 17.00 %ISO, 25.55 %ISO, 5.89 km and 3.97 kPa.m²/g, respectively. Chemicals were supplied by Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).

A. Pulp Bleaching

P. brutia pulps were bleached with sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) under four different conditions, which are listed in Table 1. NaClO charge, consistency, time and temperature were held constant, but the charge of NaBH₄ was varied during the bleaching process.

Table 1. *P. brutia* pulp bleaching conditions

Conditions	Unit	Value
NaClO charge	%	10
NaBH ₄ charge	%	0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5
Temperature	°C	60
Time	Min	60
Consistency	%	10

The pulps were placed in polyethylene bags after the bleaching liquors listed in Table 1 were prepared. The pulps were then placed in a water bath with the temperature controlled by a thermostat. After bleaching, the pulps were rinsed with hot and cold water until all chemicals were removed. Yield calculations of pulps whose moistures were determined after bleaching were calculated in relation to the oven-dried pulp used.

B. Paper Production and Tests

Prior to papermaking, the bleached pulps were gradually beaten in a laboratory-type Hollander beater to a freeness of 35±2 SR. Ten test papers with grammages of 80±3 (g/m²) were produced using a Rapid Kothen (RK-21) semi-automatic paper machine according to the ISO 5269-2 standard. The papers were then conditioned for 24 hours in a climatic chamber at 23±1 °C. and 50±2% relative atmospheric humidity in accordance with the ISO 187 standard.

The standards ISO 1924-2 (breaking length - 50 mm/min) and ISO 2759 (burst index) were used to calculate the breaking length and the burst index, which are important indicators of the mechanical properties of papers. Paper whiteness and brightness are important characteristics in optical qualities. The Datascolor Elrepho 450x spectrometer was used to measure these values in accordance with ISO 2470 (whiteness) and ISO 11475 (brightness).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The yields calculated after hypochlorite bleaching processes were given in Table 2. As mentioned, 10% sodium hypochlorite was used in all bleaching processes. Unbleached pulps were mentioned as control.

Table 2. Bleaching yields of *P. brutia* pulps

Conditions	NaBH ₄ charge (%)	Yield (%)
Control	-	-
1	-	92.46
2	0.5	93.64
3	1.0	94.26
4	1.5	95.86

It was found that as the NaBH₄ charge added to the bleach liquor increased, the yield values increased in parallel. NaBH₄ reduces peeling during cooking/bleaching by reducing the carbonyl group on the reducing ends of the cellulose chain to the hydroxyl group. This reaction is observed in both cellulose and hemicelluloses. As a result, the reaction prevents yield losses and increases the yield of the resulting pulp (Çiçekler et al., 2021; Gulsoy & Eroglu, 2011; Gümüşkaya et al., 2011; Li et al., 2015; Zhibin et al., 2005). When 1.5% NaBH₄ was added to the bleaching liquor, the yield point increased by approx. 3.7%. As a result, the addition of NaBH₄ reduces the yield loss caused by hypochlorite, which generates the degradation of cellulose and hemicelluloses.

Figure 1 shows the effects of adding NaBH₄ to the hypochlorite bleaching process on the mechanical properties.

Figure 1. Effects of NaBH₄ on mechanical properties of the pulps bleached with hypochlorite

Although the chemicals used in pulp bleaching are used to brighten or remove lignin, they also affect carbohydrates such as cellulose and hemicellulose (Kang et al., 1995; Pouyet et al., 2014, 2014). Therefore, bleaching of *P. brutia* pulps with hypochlorite resulted in decreases in pulp strength. The breaking length of the pulp reduced from 5.89 km to 3.57 km and the burst index from 3.97 kPa.m²/g to 2.45 kPa.m²/g by subjecting them to 10% hypochlorite bleaching. As

can be seen in Figure 1, while the addition of NaBH₄ had no significant effect on the mechanical properties, the tensile and burst strengths increased by 5.3% and 7.3%, respectively.

The whiteness and brightness values of *P. brutia* pulps bleached under different conditions are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Optical properties of *P. brutia* pulps bleached under different conditions

Conditions	Whiteness (ISO %)	Brightness (ISO %)
Control	17.00	25.55
1	34.01	53.64
2	35.18	56.08
3	35.99	56.89
4	36.16	57.11

Boron compounds have a positive effect on the brightness values due to their bleaching properties. The effect of boron compounds on brightness has been documented by many studies (Çiçekler et al., 2021; Gulsoy & Eroglu, 2011; Gümüşkaya et al., 2011; İstek & Özkan, 2008; Li et al., 2015; Zhibin et al., 2005). With borohydride-type reducing agents, the whiteness further improved significantly. As a result, lowering antichlors promotes whiteness. Furthermore, borohydrides completely neutralize the chloramine action, but sulphur derivatives do not (Đurovič & Zelinger, 1993; Lienardy & Damme, 1988; Zervos & Alexopoulou, 2015). Using NaBH₄ in hypochlorite bleaching of *P. brutia* pulps, whiteness and brightness values increased by 6.32% and 6.46%, respectively.

IV. CONCLUSION

It was concluded that hypochlorite bleaching yields of *P. brutia* pulps increased with the addition of NaBH₄ to the bleaching solution. NaBH₄, added to the solution during hypochlorite bleaching of the pulps, stops the peeling and decomposition reaction that can occur by reducing the carbonyl groups on the reducing ends of the cellulose chain to hydroxyl groups during cooking. Although NaBH₄ prevented carbohydrate breakdown, it had no critical effect on the mechanical characteristics of pulps. It was also noted that the addition of NaBH₄ to the solution in hypochlorite bleaching of *P. brutia* pulps improved the optical characteristics of the pulps. As a result, it will be possible to obtain pulps with high

efficiency and optical properties by using NaBH₄ in hypochlorite bleaching, and it will be possible to obtain pulps with the same properties by adding NaBH₄ by reducing the amount of hypochlorite used.

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